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Book of abstracts

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Thematic area – **Cold matter and quantum simulation** – p.7

HIGHLIGHT p.8

M. Frómeta Fernández (speaker), G. Del Pace, D. Hernandez-Rajkov, N. Grani, and G. Roati, *Angular momentum of rotating fermionic superfluids by Sagnac phonon interferometry*

(n.) **POSTER** pp.9-14

21 Sound propagation and vortices in supersolid dipolar gases

30 Quantum simulation and computation with individual atoms in optical tweezer arrays

3 Tunable mixtures of 41K and 87Rb: from quantum droplets to superfluid shells

17 Assembling many-body fermionic systems with ytterbium atoms

19 Experiments with dipolar quantum gases: status and prospects

13 Investigation of Doppler heating using Rydberg Doppler broadening thermometry

Thematic area – **Extreme light and matter** – p.15

HIGHLIGHT p.16

G. Bandini (speaker), F. Avella, F. Baffigi, F. Brandi, A. Fregosi, L. Fulgentini, P. Koester, D. Gregocki, L. Labate, S. Piccinini, M. Salvadori, S. Vlachos, L.A. Gizzi, *Toward novel approaches to radiotherapy using laser-driven relativistic electron accelerators*

(n.) **POSTER** pp.17-21

8 Ultrafast Dynamics of Nitric Oxide Photolysis and Rebinding: A Comparative Study of AtNb(II) and DrNb(II) Nitrobindins

28 Hydration Water of Lysozyme Investigated with Ultrafast Optical Kerr Effect Spectroscopy

13 Multipass Amplifier Development For The 2- μm 1-kHz ILIL Beamline

9 Studying laser energy coupling in the context of Inertial Confinement Fusion (ICF)

24 Laser-Driven Proton Source for Cultural Heritage and beyond: External Beam Laser-Driven PIXE

Thematic area – **Heritage Science, Vision Science, Technical optics and Materials for renewable energies** – p.22

HIGHLIGHT p.23

A. Chaban, *ERC Starting Grant: Advancing Novel Optical Methods for wall paintings*

(n.) **POSTER** pp.24-25

6 Eureka effect, pupilla e movimenti oculari

22 Diagnostic on the Roman wall-painting into the Baia (Phlaegrean Fields)

Aragonese Castle, from a case-study to a methodology development

Thematic area – **Quantum optics, information and metrology** – p.26

HIGHLIGHT p.27

A. Pontin (speaker), Q. Deplano, A. Ranfagni, F. Marino, F. Marin, *Quantum signatures in the motion of a levitated nanoparticle*

(n.) **POSTER** pp.28-33

18 Quantum Technology for Gravitational-Wave Detectors: SMART_Q_ET Project

20 Solid state spins for quantum thermodynamics

25 Quantum noiseless attenuation of light

10 Quantum sensing and control with organic molecules

2 Nonclassical light sources by intracavity quadratic processes

7 Magnetic quantum imaging with spin defects in diamond

Thematic area – **Biophotonics** – p.34

HIGHLIGHT p.35

L. Turrini, *Nonlinear all-optical interrogation of brain networks*

(n.) **POSTER** pp.36-40

27 Optical diagnostics of liver tumors using an autofluorescence lifetime probe

11 Mapping neuronal populations with Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy

4 Engineered plasmonic nanoparticles for optical sensing and functional biomaterials

14 Optical Modelling of a Sulcus-Implanted Telescope Coupled to a Standard Intraocular Lens

29 Phase-separated programmable zwitterionic coacervates as plasmonic liquid-like boxes for biomolecule sensing via Raman spectroscopy

Thematic area – **Sensors, spectroscopy and communications** – p.41

HIGHLIGHTS pp.42-43

M. Meucci (speaker), M. Aresti, A.M. Umair and J. Catani, *New Fluorescent Antennas for Optical Wireless Communication: Towards the 6G Revolution*

T. Gabrielli (speaker), S. Bartalini, S. Borri, P. Cancio Pastor, F. Cappelli, L. Consolino, R. Eramo, I. Galli, I. La Penna, D. Mazzotti, A. Montori, J. Pelini, C. Rimoldi, A. Sorgi, C. Zhang, and P. De Natale, *Advancing infrared sources towards the quantum limit and beyond for sensing and communication*

(n.) **POSTER** pp.44-50

1 Optical Wireless and Visible light communication at CNR-INO: the PNRR adventure and beyond

12 Mid-infrared coherent sources between classical and quantum operation regime

5 LETO on the Moon: Extending FORUM Climate Datasets with Disk-Integrated Far-Infrared Observations

31 QCL-based Self-Mixing platforms for Sensing and Communication

16 Vibrational signal of plant-produced metabolites by in situ Raman spectroscopy

26 Unlocking the Terahertz Spectrum: Emerging Applications in Communication, Imaging and Sensing

23 A Stimulated-Brillouin fiber-optic gyroscope

Angular momentum of rotating fermionic superfluids by Sagnac phonon interferometry

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Fermionic many-body systems provide an unrivaled arena to investigate how interactions drive the emergence of collective quantum behavior, such as macroscopic coherence and superfluidity. Central to these phenomena is the formation of Cooper pairs, correlated states of two fermions that behave as composite bosons and condense below a critical temperature. However, unlike elementary bosons, these pairs retain their internal structure set by underlying fermionic correlations, essential for understanding superfluid properties throughout the BEC-BCS crossover. Here, we harness a sonic analog of the optical Sagnac effect [1] to disclose the composite nature of fermionic condensates across the BEC-BCS crossover. We realize an in-situ loop interferometer by coherently exciting two counter-propagating long-wavelength phonons of an annular fermionic superfluid with tuneable interparticle interactions. The frequency degeneracy between clock- and anticlock-wise sound modes is lifted upon controllably injecting a quantized supercurrent in the superfluid ring [2], resulting in a measurable Doppler shift that enables us to probe the elementary quantum of circulation and the angular momentum carried by each particle in the fermionic fluid [3,4]. Our observations directly reveal that the superflow circulation is quantized in terms of $h/2m$, where m is the mass of the constituents. Further, by operating our interferometer at tunable temperature, we measure the thermal depletion of the superfluid in the unitary Fermi gas, demonstrating phonon interferometry as a powerful technique for probing fundamental properties of strongly-correlated quantum systems.

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21 Sound propagation and vortices in supersolid dipolar gases

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Bose–Einstein condensation of dipolar gases has unveiled a range of novel and intriguing phenomena arising from the long-range anisotropic nature of their interactions. In particular, they have been shown to sustain a supersolid state.

We present recent results on the sound propagation in these new systems, and show in particular the presence of an anomalous Doppler effect. The results are obtained within supersolid hydrodynamics and compared with a classical field equation, known as generalized Gross–Pitaevskii equation. In the second part, quantized vortices in the supersolid phase are discussed. We highlight the role of the superfluid density in affecting the sound propagation and in determining the angular momentum carried by quantized vortices.

30 Quantum simulation and computation with individual atoms in optical tweezer arrays

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We are developing two complementary neutral-atom platforms based on alkaline-earth(-like) atoms to advance both quantum simulation and quantum computation, leveraging ultracold neutral atoms individually trapped in reconfigurable optical tweezer arrays. The Sr apparatus, in which single-atom trapping in tweezer arrays has recently been achieved, enables analog quantum simulation: long-range Rydberg-mediated interactions between individually trapped atoms allow the realization of programmable spin models with one- to three-dimensional topologies and single-site resolution. In parallel, the Yb platform, currently being developed in our new laboratory, is designed for digital quantum computation: the nuclear-spin qubit can be encoded in both the electronic ground state and the metastable state, Raman transitions provide fast and coherent single-qubit gates, and Rydberg excitation provides a route to high-fidelity multiqubit entangling operations. By combining these approaches, our research aims to establish a versatile neutral-atom architecture capable of probing new regimes of correlated quantum matter and advancing the development of scalable, fault-tolerant quantum information processing.

3 Tunable mixtures of ^{41}K and ^{87}Rb : from quantum droplets to superfluid shells

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We produce Bose-Bose mixtures of ^{41}K and ^{87}Rb with tunable interspecies interactions to explore novel phases of matter and unconventional superfluid structures.

In the attractive regime, we observe that a quantum droplet elongating along an optical waveguide breaks up into multiple subdroplets, revealing capillary instability in a quantum gas [1]. In the strongly repulsive regime, we create core-shell superfluid structures consisting of a central ^{87}Rb core surrounded by a ^{41}K shell. This non-trivial geometry opens the way to future studies of atomic superfluids with engineered curvature and topology.

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17 Assembling many-body fermionic systems with ytterbium atoms

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A full understanding of strongly correlated many-body fermionic systems is still a major challenge in various fields of physics. The high degree of control in neutral atom fermionic simulators is an essential feature for investigating such systems. I will present our experimental setup of ytterbium tweezers, designed to study out-of-equilibrium dynamics of fermionic system exploiting rich internal structure of ytterbium atom combined with the high controllability of tweezers setups: in particular, I will focus on our recent results on single-atom resolved detection scheme [1]. Ytterbium features make it a promising platform for metrology, quantum computing and analog quantum simulation.

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19 Experiments with dipolar quantum gases: status and prospects

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We report on the activity of our group, with laboratories in Pisa and Sesto.

In Pisa, where supersolids in quantum gases were first discovered, we control quantum phases with tailored optical potentials and we are currently investigating dipolar superfluids in uniform potentials.

In Sesto, a new apparatus will produce a larger degenerate Dy gas, with higher spatial resolution and improved duty cycle. Here, we realized the first high-resolution spectroscopy of Dy Rydberg states.

13 Investigation of Doppler heating using Rydberg Doppler broadening thermometry

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Irradiating an atomic sample with off-resonant radiation can lead to Doppler cooling or Doppler heating, depending on the sign of the detuning. While Doppler cooling is widely used atomic physics and well understood, Doppler heating has not been studied in detail to date. We have conducted an investigation of Doppler heating using Rydberg Doppler broadening thermometry, which gives us access to the full velocity distribution of the atomic sample as well as to position-velocity correlations.

Toward novel approaches to radiotherapy using laser-driven relativistic electron accelerators

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Electron accelerators based on the so-called Laser WakeField Acceleration process, whose experimental study has been mostly taken place over the past 20-30 years, have now reached a sufficient maturity to be considered for several applications. Among these, their use as compact devices for novel, and possibly more effective, radiotherapy modalities is deserving a great and growing attention. At the Intense Laser Irradiation Laboratory of CNR-INO in Pisa, research is ongoing aimed at developing a compact and flexible laser-driven accelerator of so-called Very High Energy Electrons (VHEE) beams (with energy in the range ~100-250MeV) suitable for direct electron radiotherapy. An overview of recent experiments and technological developments will be provided, and the perspectives for an actual translation to the clinical practice in the medium term will be discussed.

8 Ultrafast Dynamics of Nitric Oxide Photolysis and Rebinding: A Comparative Study of AtNb(II) and DrNb(II) Nitrobindins

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Nitric Oxide (NO) rebinding after a very short laser pulse (10⁻¹² s) has been investigated in nitrobindins (Nbs) from plant *Arabidopsis thaliana* (At-Nb) and zebrafish *Danio rerio* (Dr-Nb). Nbs are ten-stranded anti-parallel all- β -barrel heme-proteins present along the evolutionary ladder, from bacteria to man. [1,2] They display an open distal heme pocket, easily accessible to the bulk solvent, since the histidine residue, facing the distal side of the heme in most all- α -helical hemoproteins, is absent. Further, they display a proximal histidine residue as the fifth coordinating ligand to the heme-Fe atom, which is severely weakened, or even cleaved, upon NO binding; in particular, spectroscopic evidence shows that in NO-bound Dr-Nb(II) the proximal bond is absent, whereas in At-Nb(II) NO binding induces a structural stress. Noteworthy, NO geminate recombination is very fast in both Nb(II) proteins, being essentially completed within 3 × 10⁻¹¹ s and involving 80% of the photo-dissociated molecules. [3] This behavior is drastically different from what observed in α -helical heme-proteins, such as myoglobin and hemoglobin, which show a multiphasic and slower geminate rebinding process. Thus, it suggests that the open heme pocket does not facilitate the outward diffusion of the photo-dissociated NO, but instead the lack of residues in the immediate proximity likely helps the ligand to keep an optimal space configuration for fast rebinding. The dissection of outward and inward ligand pathway steps allows a better comprehension of determinants for NO binding to heme-proteins, a crucial event for blood flow regulation in poorly vascularized tissues, like the eye's retina.

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28 Hydration Water of Lysozyme Investigated with Ultrafast Optical Kerr Effect Spectroscopy

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Water is of fundamental importance for the development of life as the main biological processes take place in aqueous environments. Water molecules can strongly influence the structure and functions of biological molecules, such as proteins and nucleic acids. Different techniques have been utilized to investigate the dynamics of water molecules at the protein-water interface across a large range of time scales. Despite some agreement on the mechanisms and dynamics of water-protein interactions, there remain several critical points to consider. We present a time-resolved optical Kerr effect spectroscopic investigation into the structural and vibrational dynamics of hydration water in lysozyme-water samples. By varying the protein concentration, we distinguish the contribution of hydration water from that of bulk water and the protein itself. Our results provide experimental evidence for the existence of two distinct structural dynamics of hydration water: one associated with hydrogen bond exchange relaxation and the other with the reorganization of water molecules driven by protein structural fluctuations. Furthermore, we evaluate the vibrational dynamics of the hydration water layer down to sub-picosecond time scales. Notably, our concentration-dependent analysis suggests the presence of a crossover point at a specific protein concentration, marking a transition between two clustering regimes with distinct hydration characteristics. This threshold may be linked to protein crowding effects, offering insights into the behavior of hydration water in dense protein environments.

15 Multipass Amplifier Development For The 2- μ m 1-kHz ILIL Beamline

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Thin disks are an effective solution for high average power laser amplifiers with cooling achieved in the active mirror configuration. In this case, edge pumping can be used to efficiently couple the diode energy to the gain region, while leaving free access to the gain region for complex multi-pass amplifier geometries.[1]. Here we present the development [2] of a multipass amplifier to be integrate in the APOLLO laser at ILIL (Intense Laser Irradiation Laboratory) in Pisa. The amplifier input is characterized by an eye-safe 2- μ m laser pulse with ≥ 1 mJ energy and a repetition rate of 1kHz. The ceramic active medium disk Tm 3+ :Lu 2 O 3 is directly pumped at 800 nm, using diodes operating in (quasi) CW mode. The gain factor is 10, for a final energy ≥ 10 mJ. The scalability of the design allows to consider further amplification stages with the same geometry up to ≥ 500 mJ while maintaining the same repetition rate of 1 kHz. Multi-pulse extraction combined with cross-relaxation, diode pumping and high absorption of the active medium also ensure an high efficiency of whole the system.

9 Studying laser energy coupling in the context of Inertial Confinement Fusion (ICF)

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After the breakthrough in laser fusion in December 2022, when ignition was achieved at the National Ignition Facility (NIF), the goal of laser fusion energy production has received renewed interest. At NIF the indirect-drive scheme, where laser energy is converted to X-rays which then illuminate the fusion capsule, is adopted. This scheme uses complicated hohlraum targets and suffers from inefficiency due to the conversion of laser energy into X-rays. A much simpler scheme and promising candidate to achieve higher gains is the direct-drive approach, where lasers irradiate the fuel capsule directly. Nevertheless, in the direct-drive approach, and in particular in high-gain advanced schemes such as the Shock Ignition approach, laser energy coupling to the plasma can be degraded due to the development of hydrodynamic and parametric instabilities. Here we present our experimental studies on laser energy coupling in the context of ICF with focus on the investigation of parametric instabilities.

24 Laser-Driven Proton Source for Cultural Heritage and beyond: External Beam Laser-Driven PIXE

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Quantitative elemental analysis is essential across disciplines, from cultural heritage to advanced materials.

Particle-induced X-ray emission (PIXE) is a well-established technique for this purpose. Few-MeV electrostatic proton accelerators are used today in PIXE systems. In this poster we report on the first experimental demonstration of PIXE in air using a laser-driven proton source. A 10-TW ultrashort laser is used to generate few-MeV protons via target normal sheath acceleration. The proton beam is then guided by a magnetic quadrupole beamline to enhance the delivered flux and remove unwanted electrons. X-ray spectra from a brass sample were recorded with a CCD in single-photon counting mode and validated against energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), achieving excellent agreement.

**Heritage Science, Vision Science,
Technical optics and Materials for
renewable energies**

ERC Starting Grant: Advancing Novel Optical Methods for wall paintings

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We present new advances and emerging research directions pursued by the Heritage Science Group at the Institute of Optics (CNR-INO) in collaboration with conservators-restorers of the Opificio delle Pietre Dure (OPD), Florence. Among the projects, we introduce the newly funded ERC Starting Grant HeRiDe – Advancing Heritage Science Procedures for Depth-Resolved Condition Risk Assessment of Wall Paintings (2025) and unveil the groundwork and previous projects that led to the scientific foundation of the proposal. We also present the project roadmap ahead, supported by continued optical instrumentation upgrades, strengthening Florence–Pozzuoli joint scientific efforts and expanding national and international collaborations for the future of optical diagnostics for wall paintings.

6 Eureka effect, pupilla e movimenti oculari

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The study examines the visual exploration of ambiguous images that lead to the delayed recognition of a face (the Eureka Effect). Eye-tracking data show a significant increase in pupil dilation and a shift in exploration strategy at the moment the face is recognized. Pupillometry and the analysis of fixation patterns emerge as sensitive tools for investigating cognitive load and perceptual reorganization.

22

Diagnostic on the roman wall-painting into the Baia (Phlaegrean Fields) Aragonese Castle, from a case-study to a methodology development

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In the framework of a collaboration with researchers from FORTH-Hellas and different CNR Institutes, a diagnostic campaign was conducted on the conservation state of a Roman wall painting dated to the late Republican–early Imperial period and situated in the Baia Aragonese castle (Bacoli, Italy).

Different methodologies were applied—from Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (CNR-INO, FORTH) and Shearography (ISASI), to Stimulated Thermography (CNR-INO) and Georadar (IREA) – as a first step toward deeper understanding of the wall painting structure and conservation status.

Quantum signatures in the motion of a levitated nanoparticle

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Over the last decade levitated optomechanics has seen tremendous advancements. These systems typically consist of particles with diameters ranging from tens of nanometers to tens of microns trapped in high vacuum through a variety of confining potentials which can be optical electrodynamic or magnetic. Particularly successful has been the use of optical tweezers to trap sub-wavelength particles. In the span of a decade, these systems went from inception to the attainment of ground state cooling which is nowadays routinely achieved by several experimental groups. This important milestone has opened the way to even more interesting experiments which explore the quantum motion of these massive mechanical oscillators.

In our experiment, the motion of a silica nanoparticle, trapped in an optical tweezer, is coupled to the field of a high finesse cavity. The large coupling rates that can be achieved with this approach not only allow us to reach the mechanical ground state but also to move beyond and explore more deeply the quantum nature of the particle motion. In my talk, I will showcase recent results in our group that go in this direction.

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18 Quantum Technology for Gravitational-Wave Detectors: SMART_Q_ET Project

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Quantum light sources, such as squeezed states, are essential for enhancing gravitational-wave detectors beyond classical limits. We present a compact and stable device from the PRIN PNRR SMART_Q_ET project, exploiting cascaded nonlinear processes, robust frequency stabilization, mK crystal temperature control, fused-silica low thermal expansion ($\sim 0.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and PDH locking. This technology is promising for future detectors like the Einstein Telescope.

Solid state spins for quantum thermodynamics

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Spin-based diamond devices, thanks to exquisite quantum control and long coherence time of the spin state, and tailored interaction with its environment, disclose new possibilities for exploring how thermodynamics operates at the nanoscales, where fluctuations and quantum effects play a significant role [1]. We employed different measurement schemes to quantify the contribution of quantum coherence, non-energy preserving maps, and nonclassical multi-time correlations in (thermo)dynamic processes [2, 3].

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Quantum noiseless attenuation of light

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Noiseless attenuation is a process which reduces the amplitude of a quantum state without adding noise. It enables the controlled weakening of optical fields while preserving their coherence and non-classicality. Combined with noiseless amplification, it may allow one to transmit fragile quantum states along lossy channels, making them less susceptible to decoherence. Here we propose the realization of a heralded noiseless attenuator based on zero-photon detection at the output of a beam-splitter, and its first application to a highly nonclassical photon-added coherent light state.

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10 Quantum sensing and control with organic molecules

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Developing controlled quantum systems as local probes for their environment and research platforms for fundamental physics is a topic of prime interest. In that regard, organic molecules, such as dibenzoterrylene embedded in a molecular matrix, are an easy-to-produce and highly sensitive quantum system that can be isolated, providing lifetime-limited linewidth at liquid helium temperature in the wavelength-range from the visible to the near-infrared. These molecules are sensitive to electric fields, displaying a shift of their main emission line due to the Stark effect. This well-known property can be used to tune the molecule through laser-induced long-lived charge state in the matrix. Applying an external electrical field we could shed light on the microscopic charge distribution within the crystal and demonstrate control over the spectral diffusion of the zero-phonon line. This suppression by a factor of 12 of the spectral diffusion of tuned molecular systems is a promising advancement towards molecule-based single-photon sources.

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2 Nonclassical light sources by intracavity quadratic processes

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Squeezed light is a key resource for the implementation of quantum information protocols, quantum technologies, as well as for pushing the precision limit of measurements below the shot noise limit (SNL). A squeezed state is defined by the reduction of the uncertainty on one observable below the SNL, at the expense of an increased uncertainty on the conjugate observable. Here we report on the realization of two different sources of nonclassical light based on intracavity quadratic processes.

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7 Magnetic quantum imaging with spin defects in diamond

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Nitrogen-vacancy (NV) centers in diamond have been established in the last decade as quantum sensors – sensors that take advantage of their quantum properties to detect weak signals [1,2, 3]. In our lab, we built a magneto-microscope based on NV centers, with which we can study 2D and 3D magnetic properties of matter, including biological samples. In collaboration with UniFi and UCBM we aim at imaging magnetic fields of cardiac tissues, relevant to the study of cardiac arrhythmias.

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Nonlinear all-optical interrogation of brain networks

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Modern neuroscience aims to uncover the causal principles underlying whole-brain neuronal dynamics. Advances in optical methods and genetically encoded reporters now make this possible in translucent zebrafish larvae, where large neuronal populations can be recorded and manipulated simultaneously. We present a two-photon platform combining light-sheet imaging with 3D acousto-optic excitation for fast volumetric imaging and precise optogenetic stimulation. Using GCaMP6s and ReaChR, we achieved a crosstalk-free all-optical approach to map functional and effective connectivity in the left habenula.

Optical diagnostics of liver tumors using an autofluorescence lifetime probe

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Liver cancer is a global health challenge and its incidence is growing worldwide, with more than 1 million cases per year expected by 2025. We present a fiber-based autofluorescence lifetime imaging probe for real-time, label-free discrimination of tumors [1, 2]. In a cohort of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and colorectal cancer metastases (CRLM) specimens, autofluorescence lifetime analysis enabled tumor borders delineation with 70% accuracy [3]. Results highlight the method's potential for intraoperative optical guidance and improved surgical outcomes.

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11 Mapping neuronal populations with Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy

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Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy (LSFM) has established itself as an invaluable investigation tool in neuroscience. Indeed, thanks to its fast, three-dimensional, high-resolution imaging capability, it has enabled the study of neuronal populations in large samples such as the whole mouse brain. The technique comes with its own challenges though, from sample clearing to the post processing of the large amounts of data that are produced.

Here we illustrate our fully custom experimental setups and software tools, and we demonstrate how we can leverage Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy to investigate neuronal populations in slices of human brain and in the whole mouse brain.

In the human brain, we image thin slices originating from the Broca's area. Molecular specificity was achieved by combining LSFM with an advanced tissue transformation protocol which we have optimized, called SHORT.

In the mouse brain, LSFM can be used for example to explore neuronal activity through c-FOS mapping. In particular, in our latest study we investigate the activated neuronal populations in mice during exposure to and withdrawal from chronic cigarette smoke and electronic cigarette vapors.

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4 Engineered plasmonic nanoparticles for optical sensing and functional biomaterials

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We engineer hybrid organic–inorganic plasmonic nanoparticles featuring finely controlled architectures and tailored interfacial properties to advance optical sensing and next-generation fabrication technologies. By precisely tuning particle morphology, surface chemistry, and their integration within photoreactive polymer matrices or additively manufactured structures, we obtain robust, highly responsive optical platforms and multifunctional composites. These engineered nanostructures enable enhanced sensing performance and open pathways toward innovative, light-driven fabrication approaches.

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14 Optical Modelling of a Sulcus-Implanted Telescope Coupled to a Standard Intraocular Lens

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We modelled the eye's full optical path in Zemax OpticStudio—cornea, a standard intraocular lens (IOL), and a miniaturised intraocular telescope (SING-IMT) [1,2] placed in the sulcus—to quantify image quality [3] and misalignment tolerance [4]. An external corrective lens restored a functional 20 μm RMS spot and preserved parafoveal MTF. A first-in-human case for advanced AMD confirmed optical predictability and stable implantation.

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29 Phase-separated programmable zwitterionic coacervates as plasmonic liquid-like boxes for biomolecule sensing via Raman spectroscopy

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Engineered zwitterionic coacervates form phase-separated, liquid-like droplets that act as enclosed, antifouling environments with programmable uptake of client biomolecules [1,2]. When integrated with biophotonics technologies, such as SERS-active nanostructures [3], they create confined plasmonic systems that enhance molecular signatures. These tunable “plasmonic boxes” represent a novel and promising route for sensitive and selective biomolecule sensing for biomedical purposes.

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New Fluorescent Antennas for Optical Wireless Communication: Towards the 6G Revolution

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Optical Wireless and Visible Light Communication (OWC/VLC) represent one of the breakthrough assets of the forthcoming 6th-generation network paradigm (6G). In this scenario, a new class of Fluorescent Antennas (FAs), leveraging the intrinsic advantages of Luminescent Solar Concentrators (LSCs) technology, have been developed and tested, opening for a new avenue for VLC and OWC application employing both laser- and LED-based wireless communication. We report on the realization of a bidirectional VLC system for indoor application exploiting FA-based receiving stages, on the realization of high-speed, 3D-printed transparent antennas using non-optical materials, and on the first demonstration of a hybrid photovoltaic window capable of joint solar energy harvesting and VLC communication.

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Advancing infrared sources towards the quantum limit and beyond for sensing and communication

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The mid- and far-infrared spectral regions, pivotal for applications like free-space communication and gas sensing, are waiting for non-classical light sources to become available. Our work investigates the possibility of generating and detecting non-classical light using the most widespread coherent sources and detection systems.

1 Optical Wireless and Visible light communication at CNR-INO: the PNRR adventure and beyond

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In this poster we review the most relevant achievements regarding OWC and VLC technologies, fostered by three different PNRR initiatives: I-PHOQS, RESTART-Rigoletto and MOST. All results consistently involve collaborations between CNR-INO and other CNR institutes, universities, and companies. We will review results ranging from material development for Fluorescent Antennas, characterized via a new I-PHOQS infrastructure, to the realization of bidirectional Li-Fi optical wireless demonstrator in the realms of the RESTART extended consortium and, finally, to smart vehicular applications, where optical data are wirelessly exchanged between vehicles, in the MOST national center for Sustainable mobility.

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12

Mid-infrared coherent sources between classical and quantum operation regime

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The presence of strong rovibrational transitions, together with the availability of high-performance compact laser sources like Quantum and Interband Cascade Lasers (QCLs and ICLs), has promoted the development of increasingly precise spectroscopic techniques in the mid infrared (MIR), laying the foundations for the possible development of MIR quantum technologies.

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5 LETO on the Moon: Extending FORUM Climate Datasets with Disk-Integrated Far-Infrared Observations

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Within the Earth-Moon-Mars (EMM) project, a lunar infrastructure is planned to monitor the Earth's global spectral radiance in the mid- and far-infrared. The Lunar Earth Temperature Observatory (LETO), will host a Fourier Transform Spectro-radiometer (LETO-FTS) and an imager (LETO-IMG) and will show the temporal variability of the signal between 100 and 1600 cm^{-1} and its correlations with global geophysical parameters, enabling the construction of long-term datasets for climate monitoring.

QCL-based Self-Mixing platforms for Sensing and Communication

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Optomechanical sensing systems can match high sensitivity with compact dimensions, which are core features for practical in-field applications. In this framework, self-mixing technique offers a compact scheme where the laser acts as both source and detector. We present here two compact QCL-based self-mixing platforms using a membrane as transducer for near- to mid- IR information conversion and photoacoustic trace-gas sensing, respectively.

16 Vibrational signal of plant-produced metabolites by in situ Raman spectroscopy

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Advanced plant pathogen identification is essential to limit crop damages through appropriate pesticide usage in sustainable crop management systems, especially in cases when the visual detection of symptoms occurs too late to allow a therapeutic intervention. Raman spectroscopy (RS) is a non-invasive method that allows for the non-destructive monitoring of the vibrational signal of metabolites produced by plants during stress processes. Because signal variations are small and biological variability is very high, a chemometric-type statistical approach is required, analyzing the collected data in comparison with data from a healthy replica of the plant.

26 **Unlocking the Terahertz Spectrum: Emerging Applications in Communication, Imaging and Sensing**

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THz waves, owing to their low Rayleigh scattering, non-invasive nature and transparency in many materials, hold strong potential for advanced imaging, sensing, and communication applications. However, their exploitation remains limited by technological underdevelopment. We present experimental progress on THz setups for imaging, sensing, and free-space links, marking significant steps toward practical THz system integration.

23

A Stimulated-Brillouin fiber-optic gyroscope

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We investigate stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS) in a fiber-optic resonator. Locking the pump laser to the resonance, new optical components are observed due to resonant SBS. Several cascaded Stokes beams satisfy the resonance condition and phase matching, so that a first sideband is scattered backwards from the pump while subsequent components propagate opposite to the previous ones. Their beat note ($\approx 11\text{GHz}$) is a candidate for realizing a gyroscope where common-mode noise is rejected using a variable filter.

Beyond PNRR. Connecting in the new R&D Ecosystem

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